

Ethiopia's Roaring towards Ending Cholera: Lessons Learned from the implementation of Stop Cholera Together initiative in Eastern Ethiopia.

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Abstract

Cholera remains one of the major public health problems in developing countries and causes significant mortality and morbidity. In Ethiopia, since August 2022, 44,207 cases and 571 deaths (CFR=1.29%) were reported as of 28 April 2024. This persistent outbreak was continued for 28 months in the country. Thus, a new initiative Stop Cholera Together was designed and implemented throughout the country to interrupt cholera transmission through enhanced multisector interventions. So, this study aims to assess the lessons learned from the implementation of Stop Cholera Together initiative in Eastern Ethiopia

The Ethiopian Public Health Institute with the Ministry of Health and partners developed and implemented a new initiative called 'Stop Cholera Together' to control and prevent prolonged cholera outbreaks in Ethiopia. The main pillars of Stop Cholera Together initiatives are coordination and leadership, surveillance and case management, risk communication and community engagement, water, sanitation, and hygiene, oral cholera vaccination, operational support and logistics, monitoring and evaluation.

Stop Cholera Together initiative enhanced the multisector engagement and collaboration in cholera outbreak interventions. This groundbreaking initiative effectively declined the load of cholera cases in Ethiopia. We recommended sustaining the initiative, equity engagement of all relevant multisector in the cholera interventions, and financing the sector to support the effectiveness of interventions to accelerate the achievement towards ending cholera in Ethiopia, moreover globally.

Keywords: Cholera, Outbreak, Multisector, Interventions, Prevention

What is already known on this topic

- Cholera is infectious disease transmitted through contained water and food
- Cholera remains pertinent public health problem in developing countries.
- Multisectoral engagement significant for cholera prevention and control

What this study adds

- Share the applied lessons from stop cholera together initiative
- The Stop Cholera Together initiative enhanced coordination among key sectors and partners, resulting in effective control and prevention of cholera outbreaks.
- Stop cholera together initiative robust monitoring and evaluation of multisector interventions leading to accelerate progress towards ending cholera.

How this study might affect research, practice or policy

- Policymakers can adapt and utilize the lesson of stop cholera together initiative to recognize the significant need for enhancing multisectoral coordination and collaboration to accelerate progress toward ending cholera global roadmap

Background

Cholera remains one of the major public health problems in developing countries and causes significant mortality and morbidity^{[1][2]. [3]. [4]}. Even though the global cholera burden is underestimated because of underreporting, inadequate epidemiological surveillance, and a limited laboratory capacity, studies estimate that 1.3 to 4.0 million cholera cases and 21,000 to 143,000 cholera-related deaths are reported each year^[1]. Among the global cholera cases, 90% are found in South Asia and Africa alone^{[1][5][4]}. Even though, the Global Taskforce on Cholera Control's target of reducing cholera cases and deaths by 90% by 2030, Africa continues to experience a high incidence of the disease^{[4]. [6]. [7][8][9]}. This disease continues to represent a major public health concern in many countries throughout Sub-Saharan Africa. The countries in the Horn of Africa - Ethiopia, Somalia and Kenya - have been heavily burdened by cholera outbreaks over the past decade ^{[1][10]}.

Despite the improvement of the health system, Ethiopia continues to be significantly affected by cholera outbreaks. Some of the risk factors associated with cholera in Ethiopia include inadequate access to water both in quality and quantity, the practice of open defecation, poor household and environmental sanitation, unhygienic latrines and weak sanitation practices^{[4][2]. [3]. [11]}. Given that most people with cholera are asymptomatic and true figures are under-reported, in Ethiopia, since August 2022, 44,207 cases and 571 deaths (CFR=1.29%) were reported as of 28 April 2024. The outbreak has shown geographic distribution in 349 out of 770 total woredas in Ethiopia^{[12]. [13]}.

Ethiopia is part of the global call to end cholera, Global Roadmap to 2030 an initiative that aims to reduce global cholera deaths by 90 % and eliminate the disease in at least 20 countries by 2030^[11]. To attain the ending cholera global roadmap, Ethiopia developed the Cholera Elimination Plan to achieve zero cholera cases by 2028 through the collaborative efforts of relevant ministries, and partners^{[2]. [3]. [11]}. Despite these progresses, cholera outbreak repeatedly occurred and continued for consecutive 28 months in the country^[12]. The persistent outbreak harms the socioeconomic and politics of the country^{[6], [9]}. Preventing and controlling cholera is about the SDGs 2030, AU2063, National HSTP-II and One WASH Plan achievements^{[9]. [14]-[17]}. Given these, Stop Cholera Together new initiative was developed and implemented to interrupt transmission and

control cholera outbreaks through enhanced multisector engagement and collaboration. So, this study aims to assess the lessons learned from the implementation of Stop Cholera Together initiative in Eastern Ethiopia.

The lesson of Stop Cholera Together in Eastern Ethiopia

Ethiopian Public Health Institute with the Ministry of Health and partners planned to control prolonged cholera in Ethiopia. Following the prolonged outbreak, the new initiative called 'Stop Cholera Together' was developed and implemented to control cholera outbreaks within eight weeks through enhanced multi-sectoral and partner engagement and coordination. To develop well-informed and effective initiative all-embracing discussions were conducted with partners, cholera expertise, multisector and public health leadership. Before the implementation, the advocacy meetings were conducted at the national level and cascaded accordingly. The advocacy was led by the higher political leader of the country and similarly adapted at the all-level administration system up to the district level. Implementation of the initiative was supported by the deployment of African Volunteers of Health Corps (AVoHC) trained surge teams and national rapid response teams for the interventions. The main pillars of Stop Cholera Together initiatives are coordination and leadership, surveillance and case management, risk communication and community engagement, water, sanitation, and hygiene, oral cholera vaccination, operational support and logistics, monitoring and evaluation.

Coordination and leadership

The Stop Cholera Together initiative put coordination and leadership at the heart of intervention pillars to boost synergy and drive multisector engagement in cholera interventions. All relevant multisector were engaged at all levels of administration through regular discussion and participation in the monitoring and evaluation of cholera intervention activities. As a result, multidisciplinary teams from surveillance, WASH and risk communication were mobilized to investigate outbreaks, risk assessment, and identify priority actions for the interventions. The coordination meetings of the taskforce and technical working groups were conducted and maintained regularly at the national, regional, Zonal and district administration levels.

Surveillance and case management

The Stop Cholera Together initiative emphasizes surveillance for timely and structured cholera case detection, identification and management to enable tailored and rapid outbreak response and control at the affected site. Surveillance tools were disseminated to reinforce the surveillance system at the ground level used to strengthen the early detection of the cases and intervention according to the standards. The rapid response team and Africa Volunteer of Health Corps trained team deployed at all levels for rumor verification, outbreak investigation, and contact tracing in affected areas of the country. Regular follow-up meetings with the deployed team to maintain the cholera response data flow and monitor the interventions respective to identified risk factors. The cholera treatment facilities (CTU and ORP) were decentralized to close to the communities. Cholera case management at cholera treatment facilities was evaluated against the standard and onsite orientation for health worker was conducted to improve case treatment quality.

Risk communication and community engagement

Risk communication and community engagement are among the main pillars of the Stop Cholera Together initiative to ensure that affected and at-risk communities are engaged, informed and decision-makers on the implementation of cholera prevention measures. The key message of cholera prevention measures was disseminated through all available communication channels and enhanced health education at health facilities and cholera treatment facilities. Social mobilizations were conducted using community volunteers, health extension workers and the health development army at the community level. The key messages were disseminated in community institutions such as schools, religious places, bus stations and other mass gathering areas. Community conversions were conducted with community leaders and influential to come up with local solutions for the implementation of prevention measures.

Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH)

Inadequate WASH was among the main identified risk factors indicated in the Stop Cholera Together initiative. Hence, ensuring at-risk and vulnerable communities have

access to clean and safe water and WASH services is critical for the prevention of and response to cholera outbreaks. Water quality monitoring (both microbial, physical, and free residual chlorine) was conducted for selected water sources in woreda affected and at risk for cholera outbreak. Water treatment chemicals were provided for households that used untreated water. Unfunctional water scheme maintained in collaboration with the community and partners. Latrine construction, liquid and solid waste management sites, declared open defecation-free kebeles were conducted at affected and high-risk districts. All religious, holy water sites, schools and special settings ensured the availability of latrine. Inspection of food and drinking establishments was conducted with the regulatory team and environmental experts.

Operational support and logistics.

Supplies, equipment and lifesaving goods are important to ensure organized and capable preparedness and response activities for cholera outbreak. Thus, logistics inventory was conducted to identify the gaps and supply accordingly. Based on inventory, logistics mobilizations from stakeholders were conducted, and prepositioned cholera supplies and vehicles for each affected and at-risk district were supported for the cholera outbreak prevention and response.

Gaps of Stop Cholera Together Initiative

The Stop Cholera Together initiative successfully enhanced multisector engagement and collaboration in intervention led to decreased cholera cases in Eastern Ethiopia. However, due to the initiative implemented through multisectoral engagement, it presented with limitations such as; unequal commitment among the sectors, varying priorities agenda by sectors, and inadequate resources among sectors.

Conclusion

Stop Cholera Together initiative enhanced the multisector engagement and collaboration in cholera outbreak interventions. The groundbreaking initiative effectively declined the load of cholera cases in Eastern Ethiopia. We recommended all relevant multisector equally engaged in the cholera interventions, financing the sector to strengthen the

effectiveness of interventions and sustain the initiative to accelerate the achievement towards ending cholera in Ethiopia, moreover globally.

Abbreviations

CFR, Case Fatality Rate; SDGs, Sustainable Development Goals; AU2063, Africa Union Agenda 2063; HSTP-II, Health Sector Transformation Plan-II; WASH, Water, Sanitation and Hygiene; CTC, Cholera Treatment Center; CTU, Cholera Treatment Unit; ORP, Oral Rehydration Point

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MH; Contributed to the conception, contribute to drafting the paper; took part in revising it critically; gave final approval of the version to be published; and agreed on the journal and to be accountable for all aspects of the work. YW, BB, LG, and SB, contribute to drafting, took part in revising it critically; gave final approval of the version to be published; and agreed on the journal. MW, MA; took part in revising it critically; gave final approval of the version to be published; and agreed on the journal.

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